

Question	N	%
FQ1 - Employed as IT professional		
Yes	147	N/A
No	5	N/A
DQ1 - IT role/position		
Software Engineer	28	19
IT Manager	17	11,6
Consultant	13	8,8
Project Manager	10	6,8
Software Architect	9	6,1
Network Engineer or -Administrator	9	6,1
IT Director or CIO	9	6,1
Product Owner	7	4,8
Research Scientist	6	4,1
Software Tester	6	4,1
Data Scientist	6	4,1
Hardware Technician	4	2,7
Data Analyst	4	2,7
Business Analyst	2	1,4
Scrum Master	2	1,4
Cyber Security Analyst	2	1,4
Data Engineer	2	1,4
Helpdesk Support or Helpdesk Analyst	2	1,4
Service Delivery Manager	1	0,7
License manager	1	0,7
Database Advisor	1	0,7
Decision science	1	0,7
CTO and Founder	1	0,7
Servicemanager (ITIL)	1	0,7
Full Stack Intern	1	0,7
coordinator / procesmanager	1	0,7
IT Auditor	1	0,7
DQ2 - Gender		
Female	17	11,6
Male	126	85,7
Non-binary	0	0
Prefer not to answer	4	2,7
DQ3 - Age		
≤25 years old	13	8,8
25-35 years old	41	27,9
36-45 years old	49	33,3
46-55 years old	28	19
56-65 years old	16	10,9
≥66 years old	0	0

Note: N = 147, except for FQ1 for which N = 155

Table III: Demographics part 1

Question	N	%
DQ4 - Education		
No formal education	0	0
High school	27	18,4
College degree	0	0
Bachelor's degree	60	40,8
Master's degree	42	28,6
Doctorate degree	10	6,8
Other	8	5,4
DQ5 - Experience at company		
0-2 years	49	33,3
3-5 years	42	28,6
6-10 years	25	17
10+ years	31	21,1
DQ6 - Experience as IT professional		
0-2 years	14	9,5
3-5 years	19	12,9
6-10 years	26	17,7
11-20 years	40	27,2
≥20 years	48	32,7
DQ7 - Industry type		
Medical and Healthcare services	17	11,6
Education	9	6,1
Financial services	13	8,8
Industrial and Manufacturing services	9	6,1
Public and Social services	11	7,5
Media and Creative industry	9	6,1
IT products and services	55	37,4
Other	24	16,4
DQ8 - Type of organization		
Private	108	73,5
Public	39	26,5
DQ9 - Organization size		
1 - 9 employees	8	5,4
10 - 100 employees	30	20,4
101 - 500 employees	21	14,3
501 - 1000 employees	10	6,8
1001 - 100.000 employees	67	45,6
≥ 100.000 employees	11	7,5
DQ10 - Region organization is based in		
Africa	2	1,4
Asia	10	6,8
Europe	87	59,2
Middle East	3	2
North America	42	28,6
Oceania	3	2
South America	0	0

Table IV: Demographics part 2

Question	1	2	3	4	5	Median	Mode
LQ1 - I am familiar with legislation aiming to protect people that report wrongdoing related to software (whistleblowers)	28 19%	32 21,8%	34 23,1%	32 21,8%	21 14,3%	3	3
LQ2 - It is important that IT professionals speak up when witnessing wrongdoing related to software	0 0%	0 0%	10 6,8%	42 28,6%	95 64,6%	5	5
LQ3 - It is in the interest of my organization for IT professionals to speak up about wrongdoing related to software	3 2%	4 2,7%	16 10,9%	34 23,1%	90 61,2%	5	5
LQ4 - If I observed wrongdoing related to software in my workplace, I would feel personally obliged to report it to someone in my organization	3 2%	1 0,7%	14 9,5%	45 30,6%	84 57,1%	5	5
LQ5 - If I reported wrongdoing related to software in my organization, I am confident something appropriate would be done about it	9 6,1%	13 8,8%	36 24,5%	43 29,3%	46 31,3%	4	5
LQ6 - Management in my organization is serious about protecting people who report wrongdoing related to software*	9 8,5%	8 7,5%	31 29,2%	29 27,4%	29 27,4%	4	3
LQ7 - I am aware of the procedures/mechanisms to use when reporting wrongdoing related to software within my organization	14 9,5%	13 8,8%	30 20,4%	48 32,7%	42 28,6%	4	4
LQ8 - I would be comfortable using the current procedures/mechanisms in place to formally report any wrongdoing related to software in my organization	13 8,8%	9 6,1%	39 26,5%	38 25,9%	48 32,7%	4	5

Table V: Overview Likert Questions

Question	N	%
MC1 - As an IT professional which one of these actions do you think is the most effective way to stop wrongdoing related to software? (Choose only one)		
By directly confronting the wrongdoer	36	24,5
By informally addressing the wrongdoing to coworkers or management (e.g., at the weekly status meeting or at the coffee machine)	14	9,5
By formally reporting the wrongdoing within the organization via official channels (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)	54	36,7
By formally reporting the wrongdoing to a regulator outside the organization via official channels (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)	17	11,6
By reporting the wrongdoing to journalists or news organizations	4	2,7
By reporting the wrongdoing directly to the general public, via the internet, Twitter, Facebook, or on online blogs	1	0,7
None of the above – in my opinion, there is no effective way to stop wrongdoing	0	0
Don't know	1	0,7
Other	20	13,6
MC4 - As an IT professional when do you think it is appropriate to report wrongdoing related to software to journalists, media, or an online platform? (Choose only one)		
As the first option in any situation	8	5,4
Whenever there becomes a specific reason to do so	45	30,6
Only as a last resort, if all else fails	73	49,7
Never	17	11,6
Don't know	4	2,7
MC8 - Have you ever witnessed or had suspicions that some form of wrongdoing related to software may have taken place within your current organization?		
Yes	33	22,4
No	114	77,6

Table VI: Results: RQ 1

Question	N	%
MC5 - Which of the following channels are available to employees in your organization to formally report wrongdoing related to software? (Choose all relevant answers)*		
Internal hotline	48	32,7
External hotline (outsourced to a third-party provider)	8	5,4
Dedicated email	65	44,2
In-person reporting	86	58,5
Internal web-based system	45	30,6
External web-based system (outsourced to a third-party provider)	6	4,1
Don't know	20	13,6
There are no formal channels available to report wrongdoing related to software	20	13,6
Other	5	3,4
MC6 - Is it possible for employees in your organization to report wrongdoing related to software anonymously?		
Yes	45	30,6
No	47	32
Don't know	55	37,4

*Respondents had the option to select multiple answers, therefore, the percentages are relative to N = 147.

Table VII: Results: RQ2

Question	N	%
MC2 - As an IT professional which of the following factors would enable you to report wrongdoing related to software? (Choose all relevant answers)*		
If I am guaranteed confidentiality (i.e., I share my name and know management or investigators would not share my identity with anyone)	59	40,1
If I can report anonymously (i.e., my identity is not shared with anyone)	65	44,2
If I know that I will be compensated for any harm I might suffer as a result of making my report	35	23,8
If I know that it will make a difference to those affected by the wrongdoing	90	61,2
If I know that my organization will act on my report	100	68
If I receive a financial reward for making a report	10	6,8
There are no enabling factors for me to report wrongdoing	16	10,9
Other	4	2,7
MC3 - As an IT professional which of the following barriers would prevent you from reporting wrongdoing related to software? (Choose all relevant answers)*		
Concern I could lose my job	58	39,5
Concern for my future career prospects	49	33,3
Concern that my report will make no difference	72	49
Concern that colleagues could lose their jobs	33	22,4
Concern I would be isolated by my colleagues	39	26,5
Difficulty to prove the threat or harm	66	44,9
Do not know how or where to report	38	25,9
Fear of financial consequences	32	21,8
Fear of legal consequences	39	26,5
It would be an act of disloyalty	4	2,7
Negative attitudes towards people reporting wrongdoing	20	13,6
There are no barriers for me to report wrongdoing	33	22,4
Other	5	3,4
MC7 - What obstacles would prevent you from using the current reporting procedures/mechanisms in your organization? (Choose all relevant answers)*		
I am not confident that the current procedures/mechanisms will resolve the issue	36	24,5
Reporting may result in retaliation against me	30	20,4
Process may not be anonymous (i.e., my identity would be shared)	37	25,2
Process may not be confidential (i.e., I shared my name with management or investigators and they shared my identity with anyone else)	33	22,4
Procedures/mechanisms are not clear to me	33	22,4
No obstacles preventing me from using the current reporting mechanisms or procedures	74	50,3
Other	5	3,4
MC9 - In case you became aware of wrongdoing related to software in your workplace and you did not take action, what was the reason? (Choose all relevant answers)**		
I decided the breach was not serious enough for me to report	11	33,3
I did not know who to address or where to report	5	15,2
I knew there would be no adequate response from my organization	9	27,3
I think reporting wrongdoing is not right	0	0
I wanted to protect the person who was committing the wrongdoing	1	3
I was afraid of legal or financial consequences against myself	2	6,1
I was afraid that my relationship with the management would be ruined	6	18,2
Such violations are usual practice in the organization I am employed at	0	0
The victim of the wrongdoing did not want me to report it	1	3
I did take action	18	54,5
Other	2	6,1
MC10 - In case you became aware of wrongdoing related to software in your workplace and you did take action, how did you act? (Choose all relevant answers)**		
I informally addressed the wrongdoing to coworkers or management (e.g., at the weekly status meeting or at the coffee machine)	17	51,5
I spoke directly to the person who committed the wrongdoing	9	27,3
I reported formally within the organization via an official channel (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)	11	33,3
I reported formally to a regulator outside the organization via an official channel (e.g., email, hotline, web-based system)	2	6,1
I reported to journalists or news organizations	0	0
I reported directly to the general public, via the internet, Twitter, Facebook, or on online blogs	0	0
I did not take action	3	9,1
Other	2	6,1
MC11 - What was the reaction of your organization?		
The situation has been corrected	14	42,4
The organization did nothing	6	18,2
The action is still being processed	4	12,1
The organization took action against me	2	6,1
Not applicable	6	18,2
Other	1	3

*Respondents had the option to select multiple answers, therefore, the percentages are relative to N = 147.

**Only respondents who witnessed or suspected wrongdoing in their organization answered this question. Respondents had the option to select multiple answers, therefore, the percentages are relative to N = 33.

Table VIII: Results RQ3

Questions and variables	Used test	Statistic	P value	Df
RQ1 - What is the general view and perception of IT professionals on reporting wrongdoing related to software?				
LQ1 - Familiar with legislation				
Gender	Mann Whitney	1112.5	0.8023	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	Mann Whitney	2615.5	0.7731	N/A
Organization type	Mann Whitney	2224.5	0.6076	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	Mann Whitney	2473	0.7671	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	Mann Whitney	2416.5	0.4818	N/A
LQ2 - Speaking up is important				
Gender	Mann Whitney	1080	0.9581	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	Mann Whitney	2479.5	0.4150	N/A
Organization type	Mann Whitney	2220	0.6199	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	Mann Whitney	2377	0.4977	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	Mann Whitney	2630	0.8950	N/A
LQ3 - Reporting is in the interest of my organization				
Gender	Mann Whitney	861.5	0.1952	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	MannWhitney	2599.5	0.7262	N/A
Organization type	MannWhitney	2112	0.9808	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	MannWhitney	2181	0.1442	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	MannWhitney	2072.5	0.0387	N/A
LQ4 - Feel obliged to report when witnessing wrongdoing				
Gender	Mann Whitney	977	0.5629	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	MannWhitney	2641.5	0.8511	N/A
Organization type	MannWhitney	2136	0.8974	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	MannWhitney	2166.5	0.1294	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	MannWhitney	2248	0.1702	N/A
MC1 - Perceived most effective way to stop wrongdoing*				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.7636	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	5.4061	0.2481	4
Organization type	ChiSquare	1.4753	0.8310	4
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	ChiSquare	5.9359	0.2039	4
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	ChiSquare	2.5043	0.6438	4
MC4 - Report to media				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.3626	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.0808	N/A
Organization type	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.9340	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.4689	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.6750	N/A
MC8 - Witnessed or suspected wrongdoing				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.4214	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	1.63E-05	0.9968	1
Organization type	ChiSquare	0.0130	0.9091	1
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	ChiSquare	0.1902	0.6627	1
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	ChiSquare	2.9445	0.0862	1

* For the analysis of this question, the following answer options have been collapsed under "other". This has been done to prevent violating the assumption of the Chi-square test that 80% of the expected values should be at least five. The collapsed answers options are : 'By reporting the wrongdoing directly to the general public, via the internet, Twitter, Facebook, or on online blogs', 'By reporting the wrongdoing to journalists or news organizations', "Don't know", 'By reporting the wrongdoing directly to the general public'.

Table IX: Statistical analysis results RQ1

Questions and variables	Used test	Statistic	P value	Df
RQ2 - What mechanisms and procedures are in place for employees to report wrongdoing related to software?				
LQ7 - Awareness of available mechanisms				
Gender	Mann Whitney	1064	0.9679	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	MannWhitney	2488.5	0.4353	N/A
Organization type	MannWhitney	2240.5	0.5595	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	MannWhitney	2398.5	0.5548	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	MannWhitney	2107	0.0534	N/A
LQ8 - Comfortable to use available mechanisms				
Gender	Mann Whitney	1203	0.4154	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	MannWhitney	2784.5	0.7204	N/A
Organization type	MannWhitney	2039.5	0.7747	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	MannWhitney	2493	0.8285	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	MannWhitney	1917.5	0.0071	N/A
MC5 - Available channels and mechanisms*				
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	18.6452	0.0094	7
Organization type	ChiSquare	8.4319	0.2960	7
MC6 - Possibility to report anonymously				
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	6.4734	0.0393	2
Organization type	ChiSquare	2.3978	0.3015	2

* For the analysis of this question, the following answer options have been collapsed under "external channel". This has been done to prevent violating the assumption of the Chi-square test that 80% of the expected values should be at least five. The collapsed answers options are : 'External hotline (outsourced to a third-party provider)', 'External web-based system (outsourced to a third-party provider)'

Table X: Statistical analysis results RQ2

Questions and variables	Used test	Statistic	P value	Df
RQ3 - What enables or obstructs an IT professional to report wrongdoing related to software?				
LQ5 - Confident in appropriate actions of organization after report				
Gender	Mann Whitney	1074	0.9877	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	MannWhitney	3073	0.1390	N/A
Organization type	MannWhitney	2062	0.8493	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	MannWhitney	2198.5	0.1650	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	MannWhitney	1875.5	0.0042	N/A
LQ6 - Management is serious about protecting employees who report				
Gender	Mann Whitney	689	0.9533	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	MannWhitney	1493.5	0.4749	N/A
Organization type	MannWhitney	1346	0.3378	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	MannWhitney	1076	0.2662	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	MannWhitney	1225.5	0.2669	N/A
MC2 - Enabling Factors for reporting				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.6865	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	9.6233	0.2109	7
Organization type	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.8246	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	ChiSquare	3.5768	0.8270	7
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	ChiSquare	8.7254	0.2729	7
MC3 - Barriers for reporting				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.9832	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	10.1517	0.6027	12
Organization type	ChiSquare	7.4474	0.8267	12
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	ChiSquare	8.9675	0.7057	12
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	ChiSquare	15.0596	0.2382	12
MC7 - Obstacles for using reporting mechanisms				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.1156	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	ChiSquare	3.1076	0.7952	6
Organization type	ChiSquare	2.0107	0.9187	6
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	ChiSquare	1.9855	0.9210	6
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	ChiSquare	22.0039	0.0012	6
MC9 - Reasons for not taking action				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.3844	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.5657	N/A
Organization type	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.6177	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.4034	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.0145	N/A
MC10 - Actions taken by IT professionals				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.0580	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.0410	N/A
Organization type	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.8748	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.6610	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.6960	N/A
MC11 - Reaction of management				
Gender	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.5315	N/A
Organization size (<1000 and >1000)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.5653	N/A
Organization type	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.5621	N/A
Time at organization (<5 years and >5 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.4388	N/A
Time working as IT pro (<10 years and >10 years)	Fisher Exact	N/A	0.3254	N/A

Table XI: Statistical analysis results RQ3